

The correlation between students' anxiety and speaking achievement

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to measure communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and test anxiety as predictors of students' anxiety with speaking achievement. The second goal was to determine the relative importance of the three predictors in predicting speaking achievement in Department of Islamic Education, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Tarbiyah (STIT) Aqidah Usymuni Sumenep. The samples of this research were 30 from 64 second-semester students in the 2022-2023 academic year. The data analysis using multiple regression were done by using SPSS. It found that the correlation between communicative apprehension and speaking achievement was -0.333, fear of negative evaluation and speaking achievement was -0.379, and anxiety of test and speaking achievement was -0.128. It means the three indicators of Anxiety were correlated with speaking achievement. Furthermore, the result of the T-test correlation of fear of negative evaluation with speaking achievement could be inferred that the T-test significant $0.005 < 0.05$, the T-test correlation of communicative apprehension with speaking achievement was $0.146 > 0.05$, anxiety of test with speaking achievement was T-test significant $0.78 > 0.05$. The conclusion, fear of negative evaluation is the best predictor of speaking achievement. Fear of negative evaluation provides a negative contribution. The higher the fear of negative evaluation students have, the lower achievement they have.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Speaking is one of the four basic language skills in language learning. It is the means or medium that individuals use to converse with others. Although speaking is challenging, everyone should do it because it allows them to express their thoughts or ideas directly [1]. Individuals can communicate clearly through speech, and others can give and receive answers in a short amount of time. Therefore, not everyone can participate in communication with others. Speaking is a useful skill because it allows speaking many words consistently [2].

When speaking, words are used to express thoughts or convey information [2]. This means that speech is the act of delivering a speech. Spoken language is the medium of communication between speaker and listener. The listener receives messages from the speaker, and the speaker receives feedback from the listener. By engaging in dialogue with others, this activity provides a forum for the exchange of knowledge and ideas and the formation of positive interpersonal bonds between listeners and speakers.

Speaking is the act of expressing ideas, beliefs, emotions, and thoughts through the use of audible gestures or outward physical movements in the hope that the listener understands the meaning or message. For most people, the most important aspect of learning a foreign or foreign language is developing their speaking skills, and the ability to hold a conversation in that language determines their success [3].

It turns out that in practicing speaking, foreign language learners are often anxious to do it and this is likely to happen in most English classes, at all levels in Indonesia. Azizifar *et al.* [4] claimed that “the main causes of anxiety were things like a lack of confidence, a lack of preparation, and a fear of failing the class”. It commonly occurs presently either in education or social environments that the students who do not doubt what they want to talk about will have many parts to perform in public, with high intention and faith from the listeners. Conversely, doubtful students will have little chance to be regarded and less attention by people; it seems there is no interesting place in their performance. That's why they need motivation to be more active. Motivation is a kind of internal belief that can push people to do something. So, motivation helps them to speak English precisely [5].

Furthermore, speaking is the act of using the mouth to communicate verbally with others. Speaking should therefore be seen as present at all times. One approach to discovering more about oneself is by speaking. Speaking forces one to confront issues related to other groups, individuals, and the assumptions we have made about coexistence. This means that speaking is a tool for communicating with each other; as social beings incapable of living alone, we depend on speaking to meet our needs. Sellers [6] distinguished language anxiety into two kinds: debilitating and facilitating. The first is debilitating, for example, uncomfortable feelings like nervousness and worry interfere with the process of learning. On the other hand, facilitating anxiety makes people feel positive, and motivated before a challenging task.

The case of language anxiety has been researched by researchers. Azizifar *et al.* [4], studied that there was a significant and somewhat negative correlation between the English achievements of English as a foreign language (EFL) learners and the level of anxiety they typically experience during their English language learning. The lower the speaking ability, the higher the foreign language classroom anxiety scale (FLCAS) score. Another study carried out in Universitas Negeri Padang explained that in the fourth semester of the English Education study program students' speaking anxiety showed that 82% of the students reported having middle-level of speaking nervousness [7]. In contrast, the other levels had 9% for both high and low levels, it was noticeably different. The respondents said that they experienced peer and lecturer comments, speaking test anxiety (44%), communication anxiety (34%), and speaking test anxiety (22%). The fear of speaking in front of the class was the most common speaking anxiety however, following a comprehensive interview regarding the participants' state, this study discovered that all types of speaking anxiety were present in the relationship.

Rachmawati and Jurianto [8] examined the psychological impact of learning a foreign language, in particular the relationship between academic progress and foreign language anxiety (FLA). For the study, 43 undergraduate students from the English Department were selected as participants. This study used a quantitative methodology using descriptive analysis and Pearson correlation to conduct the findings. The study's conclusions showed that the students' levels of anxiety related to learning a foreign language are fairly low ($M=2.75$, $SD=0.86$). The results also suggested that there was no correlation ($r=-0.9$) between the students' academic success and their degree of anxiety related to learning a foreign language. This study suggested that language instructors were supposed to consistently support their students in developing more confidence in their ability to learn a second or foreign language and in reducing their degree of language anxiety.

Rachmawati and Jurianto [8] studied college students' anxiety components and discovered that negative feedback or evaluation was the most anxiety-provoking in their situation, increasing their anxieties and fears. As a result, students were hesitant to talk and were unable to do effectively in a language lesson. Having so little experience was also difficult for language learners since they were fearful of falling behind during language classes. Ariani *et al.* [9] focused on examining the connection between students' proficiency in English and their anxiety related to learning a second language in 35 eighth-grade students at Madrasah Tsanawiyah (Islamic junior high school) of Sulaiman Yasin Samarinda was asked to complete the FLCAS, which consisted of 33 items. Anxiety was significantly correlated negatively with the students' English achievement, according to the Pearson product moment correlation ($r=-0.258$, $p<0.01$).

A case study carried out by Suciati [10] investigated the kinds and reasons behind English anxiety in students as EFL courses were examined. During the academic year 2018–2019, it was done at Institut Agama Islam Negeri (IAIN) Kudus, particularly for speaking skill courses of the student's second semester in the English Education Department (EED). The researcher observed class interactions and conducted interviews to get the data. Two conclusions emerged from the analysis. Trait, state, and situational anxiety were the initial types of speaking anxiety that might have been encountered in EFL courses. The second finding indicated that the students' speaking nervousness was brought on by three different sources i.e., performance, emotional, and cognitive components.

Fitriah and Hayatul [11] studied certain elements that influenced the students' anxiety and also found out the sorts of anxiety experienced. Six students participated in semi-structured interviews, and thirty

English Department students from IAIN Lhokseumawe and twenty-five students from Al Muslim University completed the FLCAS. The data were descriptively examined to respond to the study questions. When IAIN Lhokseumawe students were compared to Al Muslim University students, the results revealed that IAIN Lhokseumawe students were more worried. The student's anxiety was exacerbated by a lack of mental preparation, grasp of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar, as well as prior awareness of classroom events, including fear about taking an anxiety test. They are performance, emotional, and behavioral.

Jannah *et al.* [12], studied c the study's five causes were identified by the researchers as follows: embarrassment (fear of being laughed at), lack of confidence, inadequate language, negative feedback from friends or teachers, and fear of making mistakes. This study also revealed the six remedies that the researchers came up with, which included conversing with native speakers, visiting English-language websites, viewing English-language movies, practicing positive thinking, and learning more English vocabulary.

Syarifuddyn [13] researched second-year English students of the State University of Surabaya. Thirty students consisting of seven males and twenty-three females completed the first questionnaire in this study about speaking-intensive class activities. This survey made use of the FLCAS. The amount of anxiety was determined by calculating the average value. Students were asked to answer the second inquiry based on their personal experiences and speaking abilities. Pearson correlation between the two was ascertained by correlation. The findings indicated that although the students' anxiety was at a very low level, there was a negative correlation between anxiety and speaking skills as perceived by the students. Gumartifa and Syahri [14] studied about the significance of proficient English communication for non-native speakers. Additionally, this study offered a chance to assess how speaking abilities were taught and learned early in the process, which could boost students' self-assurance and reduce their speaking fear.

Based on the previous studies highlighted above researcher is interested in carrying out a study about anxiety using three FLCAS indicators communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and anxiety of test in various settings and with various participant levels. This study explored the connections between speaking proficiency and communicative apprehension, fear of poor assessment, test anxiety, and test anxiety. In the Islamic Education Program at STIT Aqidah Usymuni Sumenep with the title the correlation among communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, anxiety of test as the predictor of anxiety and speaking achievement.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Definition of speaking

Speaking is the act of using the mouth to communicate verbally with others. Speaking should therefore be done with as much presence as possible. One method of discovering oneself is through speaking. Speaking requires one to confront issues with one's past as well as about other individuals, communities, and our collective expectations for coexistence. It means that speaking is a tool for communicating with one another; speaking is necessary for us to fulfill our needs as social creatures who cannot survive on their own.

According to Bailey [15] Speaking is a productive oral/aural skill that involves methodically generating verbal utterances to convey meaning. The children learn to speak before they learn to listen. After receiving language input, students can become proficient speakers. In other words, if we have previously listened to other people, we will be able to speak. Speaking, one of the truths of teaching languages is the conversation class. Thus, the goals and methods of conversation teaching vary depending on the student, the teacher, and the general classroom environment. Therefore, speaking plays a vital role in communication, and effective speaking often brings many benefits to the speakers and the companies. This may be one reason why educators provide students with more opportunities to practice speaking in public and in different settings.

2.2. Speaking problems

When trying to get students to talk in class, teachers may run into a few problems with speaking. These include inhibition, ignorance of the subject, random or low involvement, and the use of one's mother tongue. Inhibition is the first issue that students frequently face. Students frequently experience inhibition when attempting to speak a foreign language in the classroom. They worry that they will make mistakes and that they will be criticized or look foolish. Secondly, students often express that they struggle with motivation to articulate their thoughts and find themselves at a loss for words. This may occur because the teacher has chosen a topic that is either too challenging or unfamiliar to them. Many students face difficulty responding when asked to speak in a foreign language, as they might not be confident in their grasp of grammar, vocabulary, or what to say [16].

Another issue is low or inconsistent participation in speaking classes. In large groups, each student has limited opportunities to speak since only one person can speak at a time for others to hear. Some students tend to dominate the conversation, while others speak very little or not at all. Additionally, students who share the

same mother tongue are more likely to use it because it is easier for them. There are several reasons why students might use their native language in class. Firstly, if students are asked to discuss a topic, they are not familiar with, they will likely resort to their native language. Secondly, speaking in their mother tongue feels more natural to them. Furthermore, if teachers do not discourage it, students will use their first language to explain things to each other. Finally, if teachers frequently use the students' native language, it will make them feel more comfortable doing the same.

2.3. Anxiety

Anxiety is characterized by tenseness, fears, and changes in physical appearance. Anxiety is also viewed as a negative mindset of fear accompanied by physiological traits [16]. Another definition of anxiety is feeling uneasy about something at a specific time in response to a known circumstance. This viewpoint, known as situation-specific anxiety, focuses on the circumstances that cause anxiety [17]. Because learning a foreign language in a classroom or other academic setting is different from other types of language learning, anxiety arises in certain situations. It is linked to feelings of fear or negativity, assessment, test anxiety, and nervousness about communicating, all of which some learners of foreign languages experience.

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3. METHOD

This study is designed by using a quantitative approach in which the data is obtained on a numerical scale. The design of this research is correlation descriptive design, Ary [19] states that correlation descriptive design is a statistical technique for determining the relationship between pairs of scores. In this case, the obtained data is correlated among communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, anxiety of test, and speaking score. In this research, there are four variables there are: communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, anxiety of test as predictor variables, and speaking score as the criterion variable.

This study was conducted in the Islamic Education Program at STIT Aqidah Usumuni Sumenep. Ary [19] argued that the population is made up of all individuals who belong to a specific class of people, events, or subjects. It means that the population is all of the research objects. The population of this study includes all students in the Islamic Education Program of STIT Aqidah Usumuni Sumenep in the second semester (2022-2023), with a total of 64 students.

A sample is a small group that is observed. For the validity and reliability of data, the researcher uses a technique of cluster sampling [20]. For the sample of this research, the researcher took 30 students. It is reasonable that the second-semester students must have high-level anxiety; since they face a new environment in a class, such as a lecture, classmate, and also a topic they are going to discuss; they are challenged to interact and communicate with those cases well. This study needs two pieces of data to be observed, they are student anxiety and their speaking score. To collect the first data, the researcher used the instrument FLCAS [21] to measure the anxiety level of the students. The data on students' speaking scores were collected from the result of the speaking test given by the lecturer.

The FLCAS as an instrument is a valid and reliable tool for assessing learners' anxiety related to learning a foreign language. The internal reliability of the scale has been reported, resulting in an alpha coefficient of 0.93 and significant corrected item-total correlation for all items, test-retest reliability an $r=0.83$ [22], and it was checked by a researcher with producing 0.799 alpha cronbach. This consists of thirty-three items and was translated into Indonesian to prevent the impact on English proficiency and was checked by an experienced lecturer of English. Three indicators are used to measure the anxiety levels of the students. These are communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and anxiety about tests.

For the validity of the speaking test, the lecture used construct and content validity. Construct validity evidence comes from the assessment instrument used [23]. In this study in measuring the students' speaking ability the lecturer divides the students into some groups and each group has a topic given by the lecturer. Each group consists of three to four students, they have to discuss the topic and say anything they want, and they can ask each other for clarification or help. The most important thing, they should speak as much as they can in front of the lecture. To make the other the student who hasn't got their turn can stay out of the class and not disturb. And for content validity aspects of the speaking scoring are: pronunciation 20, vocabulary 20, grammar 20, fluency 20, and accuracy 20. For reliability, Mohajan and Haradhan [24] said reliability depends on the nature of the group tested, the test content, and the condition of testing. In this study, to avoid the errors of either underestimating or overestimating the true level of their speaking ability,

the scoring is conducted in the best conducive to make sure that the lecture and students are in the best condition and make sure that the result is objective. The time allocation for each group to discuss the topic is not more than ten minutes.

These are the steps of collecting and interpreting data. The first, distributing the questionnaire FLCAS. The questionnaire that is used in this research is a FLCAS questionnaire. The researcher distributed it to the respondents and gave the respondents fifteen minutes to fill out the questionnaires. The second is calculating the FLCAS. After distributing the questionnaires, the researcher analyzes the results of the questionnaire and calculates the level of the student's anxiety about language learning score by counting the score of each respondent. The third is collecting data about students speaking scores. The researcher collected the midterm speaking scores from English-speaking lectures. Then, investigate the correlation between FLCAS and speaking score using product moment correlation analysis. The last is interpreting the result. It is the last way in the data collecting method by which the researcher interprets the result after investigation.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Level (FLCAS) of English class in Department of Islamic Education STIT Aqidah Usyuni

Based on data collection carried out by researchers. The distribution of student scores revealed varying levels of achievement across the group. It was found that there is 1 student (1%) got between 90–100 score, which they considered excellent, and 5 students (5%) got scores between 75–89 score they predicated as very good score, also there are 14 students (49%) got score between 65–74, they can be said as good score, and the last there are 10 students (40%) were poor score because they got a score between 0–64 score. This distribution of scores, summarized in Table 1, provides insight into the varying performance levels among the students.

Table 1. Students speaking score

Categories	Range	Frequencies	Percentage (%)
Excellent	90–100	1	1
Very good	78–89	5	5
Good	65–74	14	49
Poor	0–64	10	40

4.2. Findings of the coefficient inter-correlation analysis

Here is the analysis result of the intercorrelation between communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and anxiety of test with speaking achievement. This analysis aimed to investigate the relationships among these variables. The findings revealed significant correlations between communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and anxiety of tests. After doing a correlation calculation, the result showed that the correlation between communicative apprehension and speaking score was -0.333. It means communicative apprehension and speaking score have a negative correlation. This negative correlation indicates that as communicative apprehension increases, the speaking score tends to decrease. In other words, higher levels of anxiety and apprehension about communication are associated with lower performance in Speaking score, as presented in Table 2.

After doing a correlation calculation for fear of negative evaluation and speaking achievement the result is -0.379 as presented in Table 3. It means that fear of negative evaluation and speaking Score have a negative correlation. This indicates a negative correlation between fear of negative evaluation and speaking score. In other words, as the fear of negative evaluation increases, the speaking score tends to decrease. Based on correlation calculation, the correlation between anxiety on tests and speaking scores was -0.128 as presented in Table 4. It means the anxiety of the test and speaking score have a negative correlation. This means that there is a negative correlation between test anxiety and speaking scores. In other words, as test anxiety increases, speaking scores tend to decrease. This negative relationship suggests that students who experience higher levels of anxiety during tests are likely to perform worse in speaking assessments.

Table 2. Correlation between communicative apprehension and speaking score

		Com_apprehension	Speaking_score
Com_apprehension	Pearson correlation	1	-0.333**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	30	30
Speaking_score	Pearson correlation	-0.333**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	30	30

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 3. Correlation between fear of negative evaluation and speaking achievement

		Speaking_score	Fear_negatifevaluation
Speaking_score	Pearson correlation	1	-0.379**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	30	30
Fear_negatifevaluation	Pearson correlation	-0.379**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	30	30

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 4. The correlation between anxiety of test and speaking achievement

		Speaking_score	Test_anxiety
Speaking_score	Pearson correlation	1	-0.128
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.164
	N	30	30
Test_anxiety	Pearson correlation	-0.128	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.164	
	N	30	30

4.3. Findings of the multiple regression analysis

The use of multiple regression analysis in this research is to find out the correlation of the combination of predictor variables to the criterion and to determine the importance of predictor variables. From Table 5, it is evident that the correlation (r) between the criterion variable (speaking achievement) and the linear combination of the predictor variables (communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and anxiety of test) was 0.418. The square of the multiple correlation coefficient (r square) was 0.175. Therefore, the researcher could determine that approximately 17% of the speaking achievement score was contributed from the variance of combined communicative apprehension, fear negative evaluation, and test of anxiety.

In line with the data in Table 6, it could be concluded that F test sig. $0.000 < 0.05$. So, the null hypothesis was found to be false. It denotes that the hypothesis was accepted. It means that the three anxiety indicators, including communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and test anxiety, all have significant effects on the speaking achievement of Islamic Education students STIT Aqidah Usyuni Sumenep. From Table 7, a fear of negative evaluation is the best predictor of speaking achievement among the three predictors of anxiety. Fear of negative evaluation contributes negatively in this case. That is the greater students' fear of negative evaluation, the lower their speaking achievement.

Table 5. Correlation between predictor variables and criterion variable

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate
1.	0.418 ^a	0.175	0.153	7.055

a. Predictors: (constant), test_anxiety, com_apprehension, fear_negatifevaluation

Table 6. Contribution of three predictors to speaking achievement

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1. Regression	1220.704	3	406.901	8.176	0.000 ^b
Residual	5773.287	116	49.770		
Total	6993.992	119			

a. Dependent variable: speaking_score

b. Predictors: (constant), test_anxiety, com_apprehension, fear_negatifevaluation

Table 7. Contribution of three predictors

Model		Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. error	Beta		
1.	(Constant)	91.649	4.837		18.946	0.000
	Com_apprehension	-0.260	0.178	-0.179	-1.464	0.146
	Fear_negatifevaluation	-0.452	0.157	-0.369	-2.881	0.005
	Test_anxiety	0.311	0.175	0.192	1.775	0.078

a. Dependent variable: speaking_score

4.4. Discussion

Some researchers have studied the correlation between language proficiency with anxiety and additionally the correlation between gender and anxiety, native language proficiency, learning methods,

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anxiety, and coping mechanisms. Particularly, anxiety is thought to be a major factor in predicting student progress and achievement in language learning settings [25]. Test anxiety (the fear of exams, quizzes, and other activities used to evaluate one's competence), communication apprehension (the fear of communicating with others), and fear of negative evaluation (the concern about how others view the speaker) can all be linked to anxiety related to learning a foreign language [26]. When students are anxious, they find it difficult to focus on their studies and may struggle when executing speaking tasks.

Senel [27] said that language anxiety was classified into two types: debilitating and facilitating. Debilitating anxiety involves unpleasant sentiments like nervousness and concern that disrupt the process of learning. Facilitating anxiety, on the other hand, affects people in a good, inspiring manner, best characterized as nervousness about a challenging task. The participants in this study had a high degree of anxiety, which has a negative correlation with their speaking success. According to the results of the FLCAS, the majority of pupils are nervous and suffer from debilitating anxiety.

This research proved that both communicative apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and anxiety about tests correlate significantly to speaking achievement. If the student has a high level of anxiety, the student has a poor speaking score, contradictory, if they have a low level of anxiety, they have a good speaking score, which means the appropriate level of anxiety is low level. It is proven by the test of anxiety with the score.

Senel [27] also stated that students' anxiety has a negative correlation to their speaking ability because they are very anxious about having tests or when they are following English class it can make them cannot join the class comfortably. Kamil *et al.* [28], argues that one of the emotional aspects influencing the success of learning a foreign language is anxiety. Moreover, the fear of negative evaluation has a negative contribution to speaking performance as a result they have poor scores in speaking class, and poor speaking ability can be caused by their anxiety. It proved by Tursila's [29] research about the correlation of anxiety of English learning and speaking ability of LP3I Sidoarjo business and technology college students, that there is an important correlation between students' speaking abilities and their anxiety. Yaniafari and Rihardini [30] explains in their research that knowing that other learners are more proficient in language, particularly speaking, can serve as inspiration for students to improve. Hopko *et al.* [31], stated that a student who has high levels of anxiety might fail academically because they are easily distracted and have poor verbal working memory abilities.

Also proved by Chuan [32], it focuses on the relationship or connection between English language learners in Taipei, Taiwan's emotional intelligence and anxiety related to learning a foreign language. He found a connection between anxiety related to learning a foreign language and overall emotional intelligence. The result revealed that gender differences influence how emotional intelligence abilities are used. According to this study, students in Islamic Education, STIT Aqidah Usymuni Sumenep, have a high anxiety level and are unable to execute anything like a subject in speaking class due to factors such as the mood of the class and the lecture. The focus of second language acquisition research has shifted from external factors that educators may influence to internal aspects of the learner.

Anxiety is typically a response to thoughts of a current or future threat, whereas sadness is frequently a reaction to previous poor consequences [33]. As a result, certain public speakers probably have the most anxiety before and during their speech, followed by greater feelings of despair thereafter, particularly if their perspective or appraisal of the speech performance is bad. In addition to post-speaking sadness, a persistent underlying depressive tendency can have a severe impact on a speaker's preparation and performance, leading to overall anxiety about the speaking experience. The detrimental consequences of depressed thinking have been described using the learned helplessness hypothesis.

Speaking is an element of communication that involves several factors. An emotional factor is one of the components of psychology. Tuan and Mai [34], said emotional variables include inadequate motivation, a lack of self-confidence, and feelings of anxiousness. According to Witt and Roberts [35], anxiety arises as a result of prior unpleasant experiences and or a perceived lack of control over external situations; some depressed people believe that everything they try in the future will be in vain. Student speakers with depressed thinking, for example, may see an impending speech performance as doomed to failure, given prior experience in comparable circumstances and/or low internal expectations for success [36]. Various elements contribute to students' fear during speaking. Depressed people are more prone to create unfavorable internal attributions and modest expectations inside for achievement. Some variables influence students' anxiousness during speaking. People who are depressed tend to attribute bad things to themselves and attribute failure either actual or anticipated to their incapacity to achieve or, in this example, to deliver a powerful speech in public.

Also, in line with this, some research has shown that language anxiety provides four negative potential effects on academic achievement, for example, communication skills, oral proficiency, listening skills, writing skills, and reading comprehension. Syahrozi *et al.* [37], explained that most of the students reveal that high of anxious learners have lower grades than their less anxious learners. For this reason, teachers must develop a less

intimidating atmosphere so that language learners can feel more at ease and learn more efficiently [38]. Higher anxiety levels are associated with less enthusiasm to communicate in the classroom.

5. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study provide strong evidence that there is a correlation between the criterion variable (speaking achievement) and the linear combination of the predictor variables (test anxiety, fear of a negative evaluation, and communicative apprehension) based on the findings of this study and the discussion that follows. Therefore, speaking achievement was negatively impacted by tests of anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, and communicative apprehension. Furthermore, the result of the T-test correlation of fear of negative evaluation with speaking achievement could be inferred that the T-test significant $0.005 < 0.05$, the T-test correlation of communicative apprehension with speaking achievement was $0.146 > 0.05$ and the result of anxiety of test with speaking achievement was T-test significant $0.78 > 0.05$. It can be concluded, from the three predictors of anxiety, that fear of negative evaluation is the best predictor of speaking achievement. In this case, fear of negative evaluation provides a negative contribution. That is, the higher the fear of negative evaluation students have, the lower speaking achievement they have.

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